

Individual Differences in the Speaking Classroom of English as a Foreign Language: Why Personality Traits, Willingness to Communicate, Self-Efficacy, and Learning Preferences Matter?

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Abstract

This study investigates the role of English language learners' individual differences in the speaking classroom. It examines, from an ecological perspective, how English as a foreign language learners' personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences interact with the learning environment in the development of their speaking skills. An action research was undertaken to collect data from the participants. The discussion of these data within the theoretical framework composed of Systemic Functional Linguistic theory, the Big Five Personality traits model, and the ecological theory of learning reveal that the development of learners' speaking skills is heavily influenced by the interconnection between personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences. The findings highlight the importance of integrating learners' individual differences into the teaching content and practices since their ignorance can lead to difficulties in speaking. Our suggestions to improve the situation lies in three key points: the identification and integration of individual differences in the speaking curriculum; a dynamic adjustment of classroom activities to fit in learners' individual differences through differentiated instruction and personalized feedback, and the implementation of public speaking training for anxiety reduction during speaking activities.

Keywords: *Personality traits, Willingness to communicate, Self-efficacy, learning preferences, Language Didactics.*

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Introduction

Individual differences (IDs) are among the main factors that affect the learning process and learners' performances in English as a Foreign Language Learning (EFL). Dörnyei (2005) contends that their ignorance can negatively affect the learning outcomes,

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resulting in demotivation and increased anxiety. Among the main language skills, speaking, considered as one of the most challenging to develop, generates higher level of anxiety and apprehension which might be related to some deficiencies in considering learners IDs in the teaching content and practices.

If the role of EFL learners IDs on the development of their speaking skill has already been investigated (Dörnyei, 2005; Gregersen & MacIntyre, 2014); it should be acknowledged that few research have simultaneously examine the interplay between them, especially personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences in EFL speaking development. While the individual role of learners' IDs on the learning process is undeniable; learning outcomes are actually the results of the interplay between these IDs, the teaching content and practices, and the learning environment as well (Ellis, 1997). This highlights the need to undertake a more holistic approach to investigate how these four IDs collectively and simultaneously impact the development of EFL learners' speaking proficiency.

This study deals with that issue by examining from an ecological perspective the interplay between personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, learning preferences, and the learning environment in the development of EFL learners' speaking skills. The final aim is to suggest informed didactic choices to identify and include them in the teaching content and practices aiming at developing EFL learners' speaking skills.

The main research question this study addresses is as follows: How do learners' IDs—specifically personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences—interact with the learning environment to influence the development of EFL learners' speaking skills? This main research question calls for the following operational ones: How do these IDs collectively affect EFL learners' engagement in the speaking activities? To what extent their ignorance in the teaching content explains EFL learners' difficulties in speaking?

The main objective of this study is to examine how personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences collectively interact with the learning environment to affect the development of EFL learners' speaking skills. This main objective calls for the following operational ones: analyze the collective influence of personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences on learners' engagement in the speaking activities; explain the link between the ignorance of these IDs and EFL learners' difficulties in speaking.

The main research hypothesis that drives this study is that EFL learners' difficulties in speaking are related to the ignorance of their IDs in the teaching content and practices.

Conceptual Framework

Review of Literature

This study investigates how personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-confidence, and learning preferences simultaneously interact with the learning environment, i.e. the speaking classroom, to affect the development of EFL learners' speaking skills. If the influence of these individual differences on speaking skills has been independently studied; there is limited research on how these four factors interact to influence speaking development.

McCrae & John (1992) argued that personality traits influence learners' behavior in the classroom and their ability to engage in speaking activities. This suggests that personality traits need to be considered when designing speaking activities to cater to different learner needs. However, for Ellis (1997), personality traits alone cannot explain the complex process of speaking skill development. He believes that personality traits must be considered alongside other individual differences such as motivation, aptitude, and learning styles, all of which interact to shape a learner's overall performance in speaking tasks. This demonstrates the limitations of studies that investigate in an isolated way how individual differences affect EFL learners' language development. They do not explain how personality traits are influenced by or influence other IDs such as self-efficacy, willingness to communicate, and learning preferences in the EFL speaking classroom.

Willingness to communicate is perceived as one of the most significant predictors of speaking success in the EFL classroom (MacIntyre, 2007). It is generally admitted that learners with high willingness to communicate actively seek out speaking opportunities, leading to more practice and skill development. MacIntyre and Legatto (2011) highlight that willingness to communicate is influenced by personality traits such as extroversion, but it is also shaped by situational factors like task type, topic familiarity. Further research has to be undertaken to see how these IDs interact with learning preferences and learners' self-efficacy in the speaking classroom.

Self-confidence is often regarded as a key factor in language learning, particularly in the development of speaking skills. Learners with higher levels of confidence tend to be more active during speaking activities, while those with low self-confidence often hesitate or avoid speaking. Öztürk and Gürbüz (2014) found that EFL learners with higher self-confidence perform better in oral proficiency tasks. However, learners with low self-confidence often fear being judged negatively by their peers or teachers, a phenomenon described as fear of negative evaluation (Horwitz et al., 1986). Despite the relevant information these studies bring, they do not explain how self-efficacy is shaped or affected by EFL learners' personality traits, willingness to communicate, and learning preferences in the EFL speaking classroom.

The term learning preferences is used in this study as an umbrella term referring to learners' preferred ways of learning (learning styles) and their preferences in terms of speaking activities, theme or topic of discussion. According to Reid (1987), learners tend to favor visual, auditory, or kinesthetic modes of learning. While visual learners process information best through reading and observation, auditory learners prefer listening and verbal communication; and kinesthetic learners favor hands-on activities and movement. Speaking tasks often require a combination of these modalities, and mismatches between learners' preferences and instructional methods can create some barriers to effective oral communication. Although the emphasis on matching teaching methods to learning preferences may overlook the dynamic nature of learning, especially in communicative tasks such as speaking, which inherently involve multiple sensory modalities; there is a need to undertake further studies in order to understand how other factors like personality traits, willingness to communicate and learner's self-efficacy collectively interact with EFL learners' preferences in the development of their speaking skills.

What precedes accounts for the individual role of learners' IDs in EFL context in general, with a specific focus on the speaking skills. Meanwhile, it underscores the scarcity of research investigating from an ecological perspective the interplay between

personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences in the development of EFL learners' speaking skills

Theoretical Framework

- The Ecological Theory of Learning

The Ecological Theory of Learning initially developed by Gibson (1979) views learning as a continuous interaction between individuals and their environment. In this theory, learning emerges as learners perceive and act upon affordances, i.e. the opportunities for action offered by their environment. Therefore, this theory helps in understanding how learners' unique characteristics, preferences, and abilities shape, and are shaped by their environment.

The ecological approach of learning claims that learning is not a one-size-fits-all process, as the environment offers multiple affordances, and each learner engages with them differently depending on their traits, cognitive abilities, and prior experiences (van Lier, 2004). In that sense, the theory acknowledges the significance of individual differences in how learners perceive and use environmental affordances (Evans, 2006). The concept of affordances is central to understanding how ecological theory relates to individual differences. All learners do not perceive affordances the same way since the way each learner perceives an affordance depends on his individual differences (Gibson, 1979). For instance, an auditory learner may be more responsive to lectures, while a visual learner might benefit more from visual aids (Dörnyei, 2005). Consequently, ecological theory encourages the design of learning environments that offer diverse affordances in order to accommodate a wide range of learner needs and preferences (van Lier, 2004).

The relevance of this theory to this study lies in the fact that it will help analyzing the affordances available for EFL learners in the speaking classroom especially the type of speaking activities they are usually involved in and how these affordances comply with their personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences so as to favor their engagement in the speaking activities.

- Systemic Functional Linguistics

Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) is a theory about language developed in the 1960s by Halliday. It views language as a social semiotic system meaning that it is a resource for making meaning in social contexts. It emphasizes how the use of language is shaped by the social functions we want to achieve. In other words, SFL views language not just as a set of rules but as a resource for making meaning, particularly in different social contexts.

Speaking skills can be developed through the understanding of how to use language to perform various social functions (e.g., requesting, questioning, informing, persuading). Halliday identifies three key metafunctions of language: ideational, interpersonal, and textual. Each plays a role in speaking development. Ideational relates to the expression of ideas, experiences, and the representation of the world. Interpersonal involves interactions between speakers, focusing on relationships and social roles. Textual refers to how information is organized and structured in spoken discourse.

Since SFL views language as a resource for meaning-making in social contexts, its focus on the functional use of language is important for understanding how learners' unique characteristics, namely their personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences influence their ability to speak effectively in different

situations. Besides, in the development of speaking skills, individual differences may affect how learners deal with the three metafunctions of language. This theory will help understand how the ignorance of EFL learners' IDs affect the use of the three metafunctions of language as identified by Halliday. This justifies the choice of this theory in this study.

- The Big Five Theory

The Big Five Personality Theory accounts for the different dimensions of human personality. It aims to describe, categorize, and explain how stable personality traits influence behavior, cognition, and emotional responses across different contexts and over time (McCrae & Costa, 1999). By identifying five core personality traits (Openness, Conscientiousness, Extraversion, Agreeableness, and Neuroticism), the theory seeks to predict how individuals may respond to various life situations, including learning environments, interpersonal relationships, and personal development (John, Naumann, & Soto, 2008).

According to McCrae & Costa (1999), the main principles of the Big Five Personality theory revolve around five key concepts. First, trait stability suggests that personality traits remain relatively consistent over time and across different situations. Second, the theory asserts the universality of these traits, meaning that they are applicable across cultures and societies. Third, it emphasizes the dimensionality of traits, where individuals fall on a continuum between high and low for each trait rather than fitting into distinct categories. Fourth, the theory highlights the predictive power of personality traits, as they can predict a wide range of behaviors, such as social interactions, academic performance, and emotional responses. Finally, the principle of interaction with the environment suggests that while personality traits are stable, they interact with environmental factors to shape individual actions and reactions. These principles help explain how personality influences behavior, particularly in learning and communication contexts; hence its relevance for this study on the impact of personality traits and other IDs on EFL learners' speaking development.

McCrae & John (1992) and John et.al (2008) contend that the Big Five Personality Theory is composed of five broad factors that describe the key dimensions of human personality. Openness to Experience reflects an individual's curiosity, creativity, and willingness to engage with new ideas or experiences. People high in openness are imaginative and adventurous, while those low in openness tend to be more traditional and resistant to change. Conscientiousness refers to the degree of organization, responsibility, and goal-directed behavior. Highly conscientious individuals are disciplined and reliable, whereas those with low conscientiousness may be more impulsive and less focused. Extraversion measures how outgoing, sociable, and energetic a person is. Extraverts are typically assertive and enthusiastic, while introverts are more reserved and prefer individual activities. Agreeableness reflects a person's tendency to be cooperative, compassionate, and considerate towards others. Individuals high in agreeableness are empathetic and friendly, whereas those lower on this scale may be more competitive or critical. Finally, Neuroticism captures emotional stability and the tendency to experience negative emotions. People high in neuroticism are more prone to stress, anxiety, and mood swings, while those low in neuroticism are generally more emotionally resilient and calm. These five factors offer a comprehensive framework for understanding individual differences in behavior, emotions, and interactions.

The Big Five Personality Theory is relevant to this study on individual differences and speaking development because it provides a systematic way to understand how personality traits influence learners' performance in oral communication.

Materials and Methods

The Investigation Site and the Population under Study

The purpose of this study is to examine how learners' Individual Differences—specifically, personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences—collectively impact the development of EFL learners' speaking skills. To investigate that issue, an action research was conducted since it is suitable in a classroom environment to identify a specific problem, collect information to better understand the problem, and make suggestions to improve the situation.

The research was carried out at the Institut d'Enseignement Supérieur Le CAMPUS COCODY (IES Le Campus), a private university located in Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire, within the Department of English during the academic year 2022-2023. Twenty-nine (29) students were enrolled in Licence 3 at the Department of English during the academic year. These students constituted the population under study. They were selected through convenience sampling technique due to their availability and accessibility and were composed of 26 boys and 3 girls.

In first and second year, these students received some speaking classes (Oral communication), which is part of their curriculum. They were thus able to provide us with relevant information about their speaking classes and the difficulties they encounter in the development of this main language skill.

The Speaking Class

At IES Le Campus Cocody, the four main language skills are taught as part of the curriculum in first and second year including speaking. This language ability is referred to as oral communication. In first and second year, the oral communication class focuses on involving learners into making some oral presentations in groups of two or three. The teacher selects the topics and learners have to select one topic among the available ones. The course generally evaluates learners' ability to reflect on some given topic and make some presentations.

Data Collection Tools and Analysis Procedures

Two main data collection tools were used to undertake the study: a questionnaire and an interview guide. To begin with, a Likert-scale questionnaire was submitted to the participants to identify their personality traits. This questionnaire was designed on the ground of the big five-personality traits theory. Then, a focus group interview was undertaken with a semi-structured interview guide to collect information about learners' self-efficacy, willingness to communicate, learning preferences and their difficulties in speaking.

The data collected were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative methods. The data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed quantitatively employing descriptive statistics to summarize the key findings. The data obtained from the interview were analyzed both quantitatively and qualitatively. The main ideas from the learners were first identified and grouped thematically, allowing for an in-depth

understanding of the students' experiences and difficulties in speaking activities and some of their IDs as well. These data were also analyzed quantitatively.

Results

Table 1. Results Indicating the Population under Study's Personality Traits

Personality Trait	High	Perc.	Medium	Perc.	Low	Perc.	Total	Perc.
Openness	6	21%	9	31%	14	48%	29	100%
Conscientiousness	5	17%	12	41%	12	41%	29	100%
Extraversion	6	21%	12	41%	11	38%	29	100%
Agreeableness	7	24%	9	31%	13	45%	29	100%
Neuroticism	5	17%	9	31%	15	52%	29	100%

These results derived from the statistical treatment of the questionnaire submitted to the participants of the study. They indicate the following. First, 21% (6 participants) of the population under study scored high in openness while 48% (14 participants) scored low in that personality trait. Second, 17% (5 participants) scored high in Conscientiousness and 41% (12 participants) scored low in that trait. Third, 21% (6 participants) scored high in Extraversion and 38% (11 participants) scored low in that trait. Fourth, 24% (7 participants) scored high in Agreeableness while 45% (13 participants) scored low in that trait. Fifth 17% (5 participants) scored high in Neuroticism and 52% (15 participants) scored low in that personality trait.

Table 2. Results Indicating the Participants Self-Efficacy, Learning Preferences, Willingness to Communicate and Difficulties in Speaking

Items	Common Answers	Number of students	percentage
1- How do you feel when speaking English in class?	Nervous, anxious, or afraid of making mistakes.	18	62%
	Confident and willing to speak.	11	38%
2- What specific challenges do you face when expressing ideas during speaking classes?	Struggling with vocabulary and finding the right words	15	52%
	Issues with grammar, forming correct sentences.	10	34%
3- Do you feel anxious when speaking English during speaking classes?	Yes, due to fear of making mistakes and being judged.	21	73%
	Sometimes, but it depends on the activity.	5	17%
	No, I feel comfortable	3	10%
4- Which speaking activities do you find most difficult?	Presentations due to pressure to perform in front of others	16	55%
	Role-plays and debates because of spontaneous speaking.	10	34%
	None, I enjoy all activities.	3	10%
5- Do you feel you have enough opportunities to practice speaking?	No, there aren't enough interactive speaking tasks	19	66%
	Yes, but they are too structured and lack real-world relevance	8	28%

	Yes, there are sufficient opportunities.	2	7%
6- How does the presence of others affect your confidence during speaking classes?	I feel intimidated when classmates are watching, especially if they are more fluent.	20	69%
	It doesn't affect me much.	5	17%
	I feel more motivated and competitive in front of others.	4	14%
7- What topics would motivate you to speak more during speaking classes?	Technology, current trends, and social media topics.	12	41%
	Cultural and societal issues that are relevant	8	28%
	Environmental issues and global challenges	6	21%
	Entertainment and media	3	10%
8- How would you describe your personality and its effect on speaking?	Introverted, which makes it hard to speak up in class.	15	52%
	Extroverted, I enjoy speaking and participating.	7	24%
	Neutral, it depends on the situation.	7	24%
9- What strategies do you use to improve speaking outside of class?	Watching movies, listening to music, and practicing with friends.	17	59%
	Using language learning apps and practicing alone.	9	31%
	I don't engage in any extra practice outside of class.	3	10%
10- What kind of support would help you feel more confident during speaking classes?	More practice in communicative activities, especially with real-world simulations.	16	55%
	Individual feedback from the teacher and more focus on fluency.	9	31%
	More support for anxiety and help with public speaking skills	4	14%
11- What are the main themes the speaking activities you are involved in are about?	Traditional academic topics (education, history, politics).	15	52%
	Everyday life topics (e.g., family, hobbies, personal interests).	8	28%
	Business and economy topics.	6	21%
12- Do you think the speaking activities take into account your preferred learning style?	No, they don't consider my preferred learning style	19	66%
	Sometimes, but mostly focused listening and speaking activities	7	24%
	Yes, I feel they are well-adapted to my learning style	3	10%

The interview with the population under study revealed several key elements. First, concerning their self-efficacy, 62% of students reported feeling nervous, anxious, or afraid of making mistakes during speaking activities; 69% claimed to be intimidated when classmates were watching them, and 14% said they were said to be motivated and competitive in front of others. Secondly, regarding speaking difficulties, 52% of students reported that they struggle with vocabulary and finding the right words, 34% with grammar and making correct sentences, 55% found presentations difficult, and 34% claimed that they experience difficulties with spontaneous speaking in role-plays and debates.

In terms of opportunities to speak, 66% of students said that they lack sufficient chances to practice speaking, particularly in interactive and real-world tasks. Additionally, 28% said that the existing opportunities are too structured and lack real-world relevance, while only 7% said that there are not enough opportunities to practice their speaking skills. Most students (55%) expressed a preference for more communicative activities and real-world simulations to build their speaking confidence.

When it comes to topics of interest, 41% of students said to be motivated to speak about technology, current trends, and social media. Other participants show their preference for topics about cultural and societal issues (28%) and environmental concerns (21%), whereas entertainment and media were less popular (10%).

Regarding willingness to communicate, 52% of students identified themselves as introverted, finding it difficult to speak up in class. Meanwhile, 24% described themselves as extroverted and comfortable during speaking activities, and another group 24% said their participation depended on the type of task.

Concerning the adequacy between their preferred learning styles and speaking activities they are usually involved in, 66% of participants felt that speaking tasks did not align with their learning preferences, 24% felt that this alignment occurred occasionally, and only 10% believed that activities were well-adapted to their style.

When asked about the types of activities they would prefer in speaking classes, 55% claimed that they would like to be involved in more real-world simulations and communicative tasks, 31% would like to receive more individualized feedback from teachers with a focus on fluency, and 14% would like to know how to manage their anxiety and public speaking skills. Finally, the participants indicated that current speaking activities generally revolved around traditional academic topics such as education, history, politics, everyday life, and business-related discussions.

Discussion

The results of the data collected from the questionnaire and the interview are discussed on the ground of the theories underpinning this study. This discussion reveals the following main points. First, the population under study have distinct personality traits; willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences. Second, personality traits and speaking tasks types function as a moderator of learners' willingness to communicate in the speaking classroom. Finally, there is an interconnection between personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences to the extent that their ignorance impedes the development of EFL learners' speaking skills.

The Specificity of the Participants and Its Didactic Implications

The collected data reveal that the participants have developed different personality traits since 21% scored high in openness 17% scored high in Conscientiousness 21% scored high in Extraversion 24% scored high in Agreeableness, and 17% scored high in Neuroticism. Besides, they have different preferences in terms of the types of speaking activities they would like to be involved in and the main themes they would like to talk about during speaking activities. Also, they do not have the same willingness to communicate since and degree of confidence about their ability to perform well during speaking activities.

These results have some didactic implications. In fact, the specificity of the participants indicates that they will react differently to the same teaching content and practices. The particularity of these students can be applied to other EFL contexts since the English classrooms are almost all heterogeneous by nature. If that is the case, in the specific context of the English-speaking classroom, while some activities will be advantageous to some learners, they might not be suitable for others. This could have an impact on their engagement in the activities and their performance as well. As a matter of fact, while students high in neuroticism may benefit from supportive strategies that reduce anxiety during speaking activities, introverted students could be encouraged to participate through structured turn taking or smaller group discussions. As for the extraverts, they may feel more at ease in more spontaneous, open-ended speaking tasks. Also, students with low conscientiousness might need more scaffolding and time to help them stay organized and focused on their speaking tasks. Low openness learners may benefit from gradually introducing creative tasks in familiar formats to make them feel at ease into more flexible and abstract thinking. Consequently, not considering EFL learners' personality traits could impede their performance and the development of their speaking skills.

We argue that an awareness of learners' personality traits can allow the teacher to meet the speaking needs of individual students which will have a positive impact on their engagement, reduce speaking anxiety, promote individualized learning, and support learners autonomy. By considering learners' needs, the teacher will improve students' speaking abilities and confidence, helping them become more confident and proficient users of the English Language.

Personality Traits and Task Types as a Moderator of Learners' Willingness to Communicate in the Speaking Classroom

The data reveals that learners with high levels of neuroticism (52%) feel anxious and uncomfortable when speaking in English. Among these students, there are certainly those who feel nervous or anxious when speaking (62% of the participants) and those who reported that they fear making mistakes (73%). The immediate consequence is that these students will not engage in speaking tasks and their speaking skills cannot improve without adequate practice.

In the same vein, the results of the study indicate that 66% of the participants report a lack of interactive speaking tasks, which, combined with their low willingness to communicate, limits their opportunities to be involved in speaking activities. Additionally, 69% of students feel intimidated when speaking in front of fluent peers. We infer from these results that learners' willingness to communicate is affected by both internal factors, such as personality traits, and external factors like the presence of their peers and task relevance. In fact, learners who are less willing to communicate (often linked to introversion or high neuroticism) have fewer opportunities to practice. According to the Big Five theory, individuals with high neuroticism are more prone to anxiety and stress, which directly inhibits their willingness to speak. Systemic Functional Linguistics contends that communication relies on the ability to express meaning in context. Learners high in neuroticism may struggle with context-based meaning making tasks due to their anxiety, which affect their ability to negotiate meaning effectively in interactions. This highlights the need to include in the teaching content some supportive strategies that reduce anxiety.

From the ecology of learning theory perspective, the emotional and psychological state of learners, influenced by their personality traits, interacts with the learning

environment. If learners feel anxious due to peer pressure or fear of judgment, their ability to use language meaningfully can be affected. This indicates that learners' personality traits impact how they interact with the speaking environment or classroom. The theory also underscores that learners' speaking development is dependent on their interaction with others and their environment. The data indicate that learners with lower willingness to communicate feel isolated from interactive, social learning environments. This affects the reciprocal relationship between the learner and their learning environment.

Considering the moderator role of personality traits and tasks types on learners' willingness to communicate, identifying EFL learners' personality traits appears to be fundamental since it will affect the design of speaking activities that will favor learners' engagement and contribute to the development of their speaking skills.

Interconnectedness of Personality Traits, Willingness to Communicate, Self-Efficacy, and Learning Preferences in Developing Speaking Skills

The development of EFL learners' speaking skills is heavily influenced by the interconnection between personality traits, willingness to communicate (WTC), self-efficacy, and learning preferences. The results from the study show that personality traits such as introversion and neuroticism significantly affect students' ability to engage in speaking activities. In fact, 52% of learners identify as introverts, which often leads to lower WTC, feel that classroom speaking activities do not suit their learning preferences. These learners often feel anxious or uncomfortable when asked to participate in speaking tasks.

We believed that when learners' personality traits (such as introversion) align with lower WTC and low self-efficacy, they tend to avoid speaking tasks, leading to fewer opportunities to practice and improve. Systemic Functional Linguistics highlights that language learning is about making meaning in context. However, when learners are unwilling to communicate or lack confidence, they are likely not to engage in these context-based interactions. This reduces their ability to effectively use language. Learners' learning preferences are essential in providing the right context for this meaning-making process, but the study shows that 66% of students feel that their preferences are not taken into account in classroom tasks.

From the ecology of learning perspective, the learning environment should adapt to the learner's internal factors (personality traits, WTC, self-efficacy) and external factors (learning tasks). The data indicates that when this balance is not achieved, learners feel disengaged and unsupported, which negatively impacts their speaking development. 69% of learners who feel intimidated by their peers highlight how the social environment and personal factors can interact negatively, reducing opportunities for meaningful communication. If teaching content and speaking activities fail to incorporate these interconnected factors, the development of learners' speaking skills will be difficult. In such a context, the inadequacy between learning tasks and personality traits will lead to decreased participation.

Willingness to communicate and self-efficacy directly also affect the way learners perceive and engage with speaking tasks. If these elements are ignored, learners will avoid speaking opportunities. This will weaken their ability to use language in real-world contexts. As a matter of fact, students who lack confidence in their speaking ability (low self-efficacy) may not benefit from traditional speaking tasks which focus on structured interactions or oral presentations as it is usually the case during speaking activities. Instead, they may need more communicative tasks that comply with their

learning preferences. This will help them gradually build their confidence. If these individual needs are overlooked, as the data suggests they often are (with 66% feeling tasks are not adapted to their learning style), this will impede the development of learners' speaking skills.

Thus, addressing the interplay between personality traits, WTC, self-efficacy, and learning preferences in speaking instruction is critical. Without considering these factors, learners are more likely to experience anxiety, avoid communicative tasks, and they will not have the adequate contextual language practice necessary for developing their speaking fluency and proficiency.

Suggestions

This study aims at investigating from an ecological perspective the interplay between personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences on the development of EFL learners' speaking skills. The analysis and discussion of the data collected reveal that speaking activities do not sufficiently integrate learners IDs in the speaking classroom which impact their willingness to engage and actively participate in the speaking activities and their self-efficacy. Consequently, they avoid using the language to undertake some social functions. On the ground of the theoretical framework and the findings of this study, the following suggestions are made to improve the situation.

The first suggestion is related to the identification of EFL learners IDs by means of adequate and available resources. Adapting teaching content and practices to EFL learners IDs is essential for their engagement in classroom activities and the development of their language skills. Knowing these IDs is the first step to reach that goal. EFL teachers should thus identify their learners IDs and adjust their practices accordingly. Using some questionnaires, interview guides or classroom observation checklists can help achieve this goal.

The second suggestion is related to a dynamic adjustment of classroom activities through differentiated instruction and personalized feedback to fit in learners IDs. The particularity of learners' IDs is that they may vary from one classroom context to another. They may also change throughout the classroom sessions. That is why knowing them is essential. The dynamic adjustments of classroom activities to the specificity of the classroom context will help the teacher avoid using a one-size-fit-all approach. Following the results of our study, we suggest the inclusion of collaborative learning activities based on personality and learning preferences. This consists in creating collaborative learning activities that associate learners according to their personality traits and learning preferences. In fact, introverted learners and extroverted learners can be placed in groups where their roles on the projects or activities are complementary instead of being contradictory. Extroverts may take charge of leading discussions, while introverts contribute through reflection or small-group discussions.

In this kind of pair or group work, a specific focus should be laid on rotational leadership roles by assigning leadership roles to different students based on their individual strengths. An extrovert might lead a group debate, while an introvert might excel in providing deeper analytical insights during preparation. This dynamic can help increase engagement by allowing learners to take on roles where they feel most confident.

In the same vein, designing activities that correspond to visual and interpersonal learning styles, such as multimedia presentations for visual learners or group discussion for those who prefer interpersonal interaction. This will provide learners with opportunities to practice speaking during tasks that comply with their preferences. Their confidence can be positively impacted. The Ecology of Learning Theory supports this idea, as these activities create micro-learning environments suitable to each learner's individual differences.

The third suggestion is related to the implementation of public speaking training strategies for anxiety reduction. Given that many learners feel anxious when speaking due to the fear of judgment, the teaching content should integrate public speaking workshops to help students manage anxiety and improve self-efficacy. These workshops will aim at reducing speaking anxiety by providing learners with techniques like overcoming the fear of making mistakes, managing eye contact, and building self-confidence. Systemic Functional Linguistics supports this idea by highlighting the connection between interpersonal communication and meaning-making. The Big Five Personality Traits model also shows that learners with high neuroticism benefit greatly from anxiety-reduction strategies.

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to investigate the intricate relationship between individual differences—specifically personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences—and the development of speaking skills in English as a Foreign Language context. The main research question it was intended to answer is the following: How do learners' individual differences—specifically personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences—interact with the learning environment to influence the development of EFL learners' speaking skills? An action research was undertaken to carry out this study, which involved the participation of 29 students of the Department of English of IES Le Campus Cocody.

The data collected from these participants by means of a questionnaire and an interview guide were discussed from the perspective of the theoretical framework of the study composed of the Big Five Personality trait, Systemic Functional Linguistic, and the Ecological Theory of learning. This discussion reveals that the development of EFL learners' speaking skills is heavily influenced by the interconnection between personality traits, willingness to communicate, self-efficacy, and learning preferences. Personality traits significantly affect students' ability to engage in speaking activities. When learners' personality traits align with lower willingness to communicate and low self-efficacy, they tend to avoid speaking tasks, leading to fewer opportunities to practice and improve.

The inadequacy between learning tasks and personality traits leads to decreased participation. Willingness to communicate and self-efficacy directly affect how learners perceive and engage with speaking tasks. If this interrelation is ignored, learners will avoid speaking opportunities, which will weaken their ability to use language in real-world contexts. If teaching content and speaking activities fail to incorporate these interconnected factors, learners' speaking skills development will be difficult.

Our suggestions to improve the situation lie in three main points. First, the identification and inclusion of EFL learners' individual differences in the curriculum. Second, a dynamic adjustment of classroom activities to fit in learners' individual

differences through differentiated instruction and personalized feedback. Third, the implementation of public speaking strategies for anxiety reduction during speaking activities.

Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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Annexures

Questionnaire for identifying EFL learners' personality traits

Big Five Personality Traits Questionnaire for EFL Learners

Instructions:

Please indicate how much you agree with the following statements based on your learning experience, particularly in learning and speaking English. Use the scale below to respond to each statement.

1 = Strongly Disagree | 2 = Disagree | 3 = Neutral | 4 = Agree | 5 = Strongly Agree

Part 1: Openness to Experience

2. I enjoy learning new ways to improve my English skills.
3. I like exploring different cultures through learning English.
4. I am open to using technology to improve my speaking skills.
5. I am curious about learning new vocabulary in English.
6. I enjoy creative activities like storytelling or role-plays in English.

Part 2: Conscientiousness

7. I always complete my English homework on time.
8. I set goals for improving my English and work hard to achieve them.
9. I am organized in my approach to learning English.
10. I prepare for my English lessons ahead of time.
11. I am persistent in learning English, even when I find it difficult.

Part 3: Extraversion

12. I feel energized when I speak English with others.
13. I enjoy participating in group discussions in English.
14. I often take the lead in English conversations.
15. I like speaking in front of my class during English lessons.
16. I seek opportunities to practice speaking English outside of class.

Part 4: Agreeableness

17. I am patient when my classmates struggle with speaking English.
18. I enjoy working with others to practice English speaking.
19. I am open to receiving feedback on how to improve my speaking.
20. I am supportive of classmates who find English speaking difficult.
21. I often help others when they need assistance with English.

Part 5: Neuroticism (Emotional Stability)

22. I get nervous when I have to speak English in class.
23. I worry about making mistakes when speaking English.
24. I feel anxious when I have to speak English in front of a large group.
25. I feel discouraged when I struggle to speak English fluently.
26. I get frustrated when I don't understand English conversations

Scoring and Interpretation:

- **Openness to Experience** (Items 1–5): A higher score suggests that the learner is curious, creative, and open to new ways of learning English.
- **Conscientiousness** (Items 6–10): A higher score indicates that the learner is organized, disciplined, and diligent in their English learning efforts.
- **Extraversion** (Items 11–15): A higher score reflects a learner who is outgoing, sociable, and enjoys speaking in English.
- **Agreeableness** (Items 16–20): A higher score suggests that the learner is cooperative, empathetic, and supportive in group learning environments.
- **Neuroticism** (Items 21–25): A higher score indicates a learner who is more prone to anxiety, nervousness, and stress when speaking English.

Semi-structured interview guide to identify learners' difficulties in English, learning preferences, and self-efficacy

1. How do you feel when speaking English in class?
2. What specific challenges do you face when expressing ideas during speaking classes?
3. Do you feel anxious when speaking English during speaking classes?
4. Which speaking activities do you find most difficult?
5. Do you feel you have enough opportunities to practice speaking?
6. How does the presence of others affect your confidence during speaking classes?
7. What topics would motivate you to speak more during speaking classes?
8. How would you describe your personality and its effect on speaking?
9. What strategies do you use to improve speaking outside of class?
10. What kind of support would help you feel more confident during speaking classes?
11. What are the main themes the speaking activities you are involved in are about?
12. Do you think the speaking activities take into account your preferred learning style?

